

Matrix dissimilarities based on differences in moments and sparsity

immediate

This manuscript was compiled on November 28, 2023

1 **Generating a dissimilarity matrix is typically the first step in big data**
2 **analysis. Although numerous methods exist, such as Euclidean dis-**
3 **tance, Minkowski distance, Manhattan distance, Bray–Curtis dissim-**
4 **ilarity, Jaccard similarity and Dice dissimilarity, it remains unclear**
5 **which factors drive dissimilarity between groups. In this paper, we**
6 **introduce an approach based on differences in moments and sparsity.**
7 **We show that this method can delineate the key factors underlying**
8 **group differences. For example, in biology, mean dissimilarity in-**
9 **dicates differences driven by up/down-regulated gene expressions,**
10 **standard deviation dissimilarity reflects the heterogeneity of response**
11 **to treatment, and sparsity dissimilarity corresponds to differences**
12 **prompted by the activation/silence of genes. Through extensive re-**
13 **analysis of transcriptome, proteome, metabolome, immune profiling,**
14 **microbiome, and social science datasets, we demonstrate insights**
15 **not captured in previous studies. For instance, without considering**
16 **metadata such as age, BMI, sex, or biomarkers, it is feasible to pre-**
17 **dict COVID-19 patient mortality based solely on matrix dissimilarities**
18 **observed during the first week with high accuracy.**

Metabolism | Moments | Mass spectra

1 **D**issimilarity measures are critical in big data analysis.
2 They quantify how different or similar two data points
3 are. Different measures can significantly affect the perfor-
4 mance of clustering algorithms and many other machine learn-
5 ing models. This is because different measures indeed reflect
6 distinct facets of the differences. For example, the Euclidean
7 distance, the most well-known distance, is the square root of
8 the sum of the squares of the differences in each dimension.
9 This effectively captures the average shift in each dimension,
10 aptly termed a measure of mean changes. Other measures
11 of mean changes include Minkowski distance, Manhattan dis-
12 tance, and Average distance. A notable limitation of these
13 measures of mean changes is that, the largest feature would
14 dominate the others. Instead of normalizing the dataset, a
15 different solution proposed in this report is introduced as: let
16 $P = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n)$ and $Q = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n)$ be two points in
17 \mathbb{R}^n . The mean dissimilarity $\mu\Delta_{\hat{L}_n}$ between P and Q is defined
18 as:

$$\mu\Delta_{\hat{L}_n}(P, Q) = \hat{L}_n\{|p_1 - q_1|, |p_2 - q_2|, \dots, |p_n - q_n|\},$$

19 where $|p_i - q_i|$ represents the absolute difference between the
20 i -th coordinates of P and Q , and $\hat{L}_n\{\cdot\}$ denotes a location
21 estimate of a set of values. In this report, Hodges-Lehmann
22 estimator (H-L) (?) is used. When the objective is to
23 compare dissimilarities between groups rather than individual
24 samples, we extend the above definition for points to matri-
25 ces. Suppose we have two matrices A and B in $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n_1}$ and

26 $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n_2}$, represented as: $A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n_1} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n_1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \dots & a_{mn_1} \end{bmatrix}$ and

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & \dots & b_{1n_2} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & \dots & b_{2n_2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_{m1} & b_{m2} & \dots & b_{mn_2} \end{bmatrix}. \text{ For each row } i, \text{ compute the}$$

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29 mean of the row in matrix A as $\bar{a}_i = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} a_{ij}$ and the mean
30 of the row in matrix B as $\bar{b}_i = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} b_{ij}$. We then define the
31 set of absolute differences between the means of corresponding
32 rows of A and B as $\Delta_\mu = \{|\bar{a}_1 - \bar{b}_1|, |\bar{a}_2 - \bar{b}_2|, \dots, |\bar{a}_m - \bar{b}_m|\}$.
33 The mean dissimilarity $\mu\Delta_{\hat{L}_m}$ between the two matrices A
34 and B is then defined as:

$$\mu\Delta_{\hat{L}_m}(A, B) = \hat{L}_m(\Delta_\mu).$$

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38 Then, analogously, for each row i , compute the standard
39 deviation σ_{a_i} for the row in matrix A and σ_{b_i} for the row in
40 matrix B . Define the sets of absolute differences for standard
41 deviation as $\Delta_\sigma = \{|\sigma_{a_1} - \sigma_{b_1}|, |\sigma_{a_2} - \sigma_{b_2}|, \dots, |\sigma_{a_m} - \sigma_{b_m}|\}$.
42 The standard deviation dissimilarity between the two matrices
43 A and B are then defined as:

$$\sigma\Delta_{\hat{L}_m}(A, B) = \hat{L}_m(\Delta_\sigma).$$

44
45 Dissimilarities based on higher-order standardized moments
46 can also be defined, although their practical relevance may be
47 less pronounced.

48 Another kind of dissimilarity focuses on the commonal-
49 ity of attribute values, exemplified by metrics such as the
50 Bray–Curtis dissimilarity, Jaccard similarity and Dice dissim-
51 ilarity. These metrics can be adept at capturing the disparities
52 in data sparsity between two points, hence we refer to them
53 as measures of sparsity changes. In this report, we introduce
54 sparsity dissimilarity defined as follows: for each row i , let z_{a_i}
55 be the percentage of zeros in the row in matrix A and z_{b_i} be
56 the percentage of zeros in the row in matrix B . Also, let \bar{a}_i

Significance Statement

Handling high sparsity presents a significant challenge in big data analysis. Currently, there are many strategies, e.g., imputation, regularization, sampling, dimensionality reduction. Yet, a fundamental question remains largely unanswered, particularly in the field of biology: to what degree does sparsity reflect meaningful disparities between groups rather than being largely a result of technical errors in measurement? In this study, we conducted a systematic reanalysis of datasets encompassing the transcriptome, proteome, metabolome, immune profiling, microbiome, and social sciences. We demonstrate that sparsity differences are highly meaningful and carry as much significance as the more commonly used measures of dissimilarity based on mean differences.

Table 1. Standardized mean, standard deviation, and sparsity dissimilarities of Wyler et al.'s RNA sequencing dataset

Treatment	Time	Comparison	$\mu\Delta_{HL}^*$	CI	$\sigma\Delta_{HL}^*$	CI	$s\Delta_{HL}^*$	CI
AAG	24h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.032	(0.030,0.033)	0.295	(0.282,0.307)	0.028	(0.026,0.030)
AAG	48h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.037	(0.035,0.039)	0.282	(0.274,0.294)	0.031	(0.029,0.033)
AAG	72h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.064	(0.062,0.066)	0.208	(0.199,0.214)	0.029	(0.028,0.032)
DMSO	24h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.024	(0.023,0.025)	0.250	(0.236,0.264)	0.030	(0.027,0.031)
DMSO	48h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.148	(0.142,0.153)	0.234	(0.223,0.244)	0.110	(0.074,0.158)
DMSO	72h	SARS-CoV-2-Mock	0.091	(0.089,0.095)	0.277	(0.267,0.288)	0.062	(0.056,0.071)

AAG: 17-AAG, a kind of HSP90 inhibitor; DMSO: Solvent control. The sparsity dissimilarity is in units of 10^{-3} . The relative dissimilarities can be found in the SI Dataset S1.

57 and \bar{b}_i represent the mean of the rows in matrices A and B ,
58 respectively. The sparsity dissimilarity $s\Delta(A, B)$ is defined as:

$$59 \quad s\Delta(A, B) = \sum_{i=1}^m s_i w_i$$

60 where $s_i = |\bar{a}_i - \bar{b}_i|$, $w_i = |z_{a_i} - z_{b_i}|$.

61 By substituting absolute differences with relative differ-
62 ences, we obtain the relative mean, standard deviation, and
63 sparsity dissimilarities, denoted as $\mu\delta_{L_m}(A, B)$, $\sigma\delta_{L_m}(A, B)$,
64 and $s\delta_{L_m}(A, B)$, respectively.

65 Finally, the mean, standard deviation, and sparsity dissim-
66 ilarity and their relative dissimilarity can be standardized by
67 the mean of $\{\bar{a}_1, \dots, \bar{a}_i, \dots, \bar{a}_m, \bar{b}_1, \dots, \bar{b}_i, \dots, \bar{b}_m\}$, $\{\sigma_{a_1},$
68 $\dots, \sigma_{a_i}, \dots, \sigma_{a_m}, \sigma_{b_1}, \dots, \sigma_{b_i}, \dots, \sigma_{b_m}\}$, and the half sum of
69 $\{\bar{a}_1, \dots, \bar{a}_i, \dots, \bar{a}_m, \bar{b}_1, \dots, \bar{b}_i, \dots, \bar{b}_m\}$. The standardized ver-
70 sions are denoted as $\mu\Delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$, $\sigma\Delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$, $s\Delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$,
71 $\mu\delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$, $\sigma\delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$, and $s\delta_{L_m}^*(A, B)$, respectively.

72 Often, the variables in the matrixes are interrelated, and
73 these relations, in most cases, can be demonstrated by a
74 phylogenetic tree. Converting the phylogenetic tree into corre-
75 sponding weights by their length from leaf to root (Algorithm
76 1), the mean, standard deviation, and sparsity dissimilarity
77 can be further weighted by their phylogenetic tree.

78 Results

79 In this study, we revisited the findings reported by Wyler et
80 al.(?) regarding the protective effects of HSP90 inhibition
81 (17-AAG) on alveolar epithelial cells (AECs) in the context of
82 SARS-CoV-2 infection. We applied our dissimilarity measures
83 to RNA-sequencing data obtained from these cells, whether
84 exposed to SARS-CoV-2 or not. Our results showed that
85 treatment with the HSP90 inhibitor, 17-AAG, at a concen-
86 tration of 200 nM significantly reduced mean and sparsity
87 dissimilarities (from infection to non-infection) compared to
88 the solvent control, besides the 24 hour group, suggesting a
89 weakened response to infection. Furthermore, the treatment
90 has little impact on the standard deviation dissimilarity, indi-
91 cating that the cellular response to this inhibitor is generally
92 homogeneous. These findings underscore the potential of our
93 dissimilarity measure as a tool for quantitatively assessing the
94 overall impact of therapeutic agents on cellular dynamics.

95 Methods

96 Data and Software Availability

97 All data are included in the brief report and SI Dataset S1.
98 All codes have been deposited in [GitHub](#).